

Effects of Lead and Nickel phytoextraction on the nutrient elements accumulation in shoot biomass of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*)

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the study was to assess the effects of lead (Pb) and nickel (Ni) on the accumulation of nutritional elements like Al, B, Bi, Ca, Co, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, Ni, Pb, Sr and Zn in Indian mustard. Experiments were conducted in the pots. Mustard seeds were grown in an artificially Pb and Ni contaminated soil treated with 800 mg/kg concentrations. EDTA and SA of 2.4 mM dose were applied as chelants after 6 weeks of growth. The concentrations of elements (like Al, B, Bi, Ca, Co, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, Ni, Pb, Sr and Zn) in plant samples were determined by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES). Metals and chelants effect was found in the uptake and accumulation of nutrient elements of the plant. It was found that accumulation of nutrient elements in mustard plants may increase, decrease or be unaffected when plants were treated with lead and nickel. This study will further help in the development of novel systems for solubilizing heavy metals especially Pb and for transporting them to leaves.

1. Introduction

Phytoextraction is an innovative technology which uses plants to remove contaminants from contaminated soil. Many researchers have studied the accumulation of heavy metals in different plant species (Hu et al. 2017; Nouri et al. 2009). However, Indian mustard plant plays an important role in accumulation of several heavy metals (Singh and Fulekar 2012). Hyperaccumulators are particular plant species having capacity to hyper accumulate heavy metals in their harvestable parts (Ebbs and Kochian 1997). Metal accumulator species can be used for the remediation of toxic heavy metals or organic contaminants. These goals require the understanding of the bioavailability of contaminants in the soil, their mobilization in the rhizosphere by added chelators or microorganisms and plant root exudates, their uptake to the root, the mechanism of long distance transport to shoot or to the useable or edible parts and their accumulation and speciation.

Nutrients are essential for biological functions in plants and humans. These nutrients are classified as macro, micro and trace elements based on their quantity requirements. Examples of macronutrients and micronutrients in plants are K, Na, Ca, Mg and Fe, B, Mn, Zn, Cu, Mo, Ni respectively (DalCorso et al. 2014). While Cr, Se, Pb, Cd, Hg and As are trace elements. Few studies have been done on trace element accumulation by plants in heavy metal contaminated soils (Ding et al. 2018; Pivić, et al. 2017; Taha et al. 2013). Nickel acts as an essential micronutrient at lower doses and performs as a toxic element when it is in excess. There is slight details about effect of heavy metals and chelants on mineral nutrition in plants (Nazar et al. 2012; Nas and Ali 2018; Sreekanth et al. 2013; Yadav et al. 2016; Yilmaz et al. 2009). Therefore, further research on effects of chelants and heavy metals on nutrient elements accumulation by plants is need to be investigated. The accumulation of mineral nutrients varies with type of plant species and concentrations of heavy metals. Chizzola and Mitteregger (2005) examined the effects of Cd and Zn on trace element accumulation in

Chamomile (*Matricaria recutita* L.). It was found that these metals had slight influence on Cu and Mn contents. The role of Mn in the plant metabolic processes could be seen as an essential micronutrient and as a toxic element when it is in excess (Ducic and Polle 2005; Kochian et al. 2004; Millaleo et al. 2010). Sharma and Dubey (2005) reviewed about lead toxicity, detoxification and tolerance in plants. Popova (2016) found that the higher content of Pb and Ni in the environment lower its degree of absorption. A study by Tangahu et al. (2011) found that *Brassica juncea* plants can accumulate more than 100 mg/g Pb dry weight. Henceforth, Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*) plants were selected for the present study due to its extensive studies on heavy metal phytoremediation.

In the present investigation, an attempt has been made to study the effects of Ethylene diamine tetracetic acid (EDTA) and salicylic acid (SA) induced phytoextraction of heavy metals (Pb and Ni) contaminated soil on the nutrient accumulation in Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*).

2. Materials and methods

The experiment was conducted during the period from October 2009 to January 2010 in Micromodel laboratory of Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi (77.09°E longitude, 28.45°N latitude and 228 m above sea level). During the study period, the average annual rainfall was 680 mm while the maximum and minimum temperature was between 19-42 °C and 4-14 °C respectively. The soil taken for experiment was sandy loam soil with contents of organic carbon-0.7%, available nitrogen-2.7 %, available phosphorus-8 %, available potassium-198 % and pH of 7.6. The experimental design was completely randomized with treatments control (T0), lead and nickel (T1), Pb + Ni + EDTA (T2) and Pb + Ni + SA (T3) respectively with three repetitions. The applied doses of lead and nickel were 800 mg/kg of each by using lead nitrate

(Qualigens) and nickel nitrate [as $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Qualigens)] salts respectively. Ethylene diamine tetracetic acid (EDTA) is an inorganic chelant while salicylic acid (SA) is an organic chelant. EDTA ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{K}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_{10} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; MERCK) and SA ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH}-\text{COOH}$; Qualigens) at 2.4 mM concentrations were applied during the 10th week of plant growth to T2 and T3 treatments respectively. Harvesting was done at maturation stage. Plant samples were washed with tap water and dried at 70°C for 48 hours. Dry weights of plant samples were measured.

Plant elemental analysis: Plant samples were put in muffle furnace at about 500 °C to get ash. The ash of samples were dissolved into 20% HCl (Kaur et al. 2013). After filtration, the solutions were diluted to 50 ml with distilled water. Elements such as Al, B, Bi, Ca, Co, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, Ni, Pb, Sr and Zn were estimated by using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometry (Varian Vista-MPX CCD Simultaneous ICP-OES, Varian Australia Pty. Ltd).

Analysis of variance was used to assess significant differences among treatments in Microsoft Office EXCEL 2003 at 95% confidence level.

3. Results and discussion

The results of nutrient analysis in *Brassica juncea* plants obtained by ICP-OES technique are shown in Table 1. The most abundant elements are Na, K, Ca and Mg with concentration ranging from 161 to 9722 mg/kg. The medium range concentration were of Al, B, Fe, Mn, Sr and Zn elements in the range of 15.9 to 4171 mg /kg. Toxic elements like Pb and Ni are found from 5.7 to 415.8 mg/kg. Other elements such as Bi, Cu and Co are found in the range of 0.2 to 35.9 mg/kg.

Table 1. Nutrient content of *Brassica juncea* with different treatments

Element (mg/kg)	T0	T1	T2	T3
Bi	4.9 ±0.09	3.7 ±3.53	35.9 ±1.81	6.4 ±0.33
B	43.0±1.56	68.3 ±2.94	139.1±1.66	231.2±2.04
Ca	5403.5±37.02	161.0±1.72	260.8±3.76	1316.6±2.92
Fe	471.0±1.73	55.0±2.31	172.5±2.02	337.0±2.64
K	4025.7±10.35	7947.5±4.27	6476.3±5.23	9724.0±3.21
Mg	9861±2.31	8645±4.67	9722±2.32	3560.0±4.93
Mn	145.4±2.45	56.7±4.97	109.6±2.34	95.0±2.31
Na	2166.6±39.26	1569±11.85	1506.6±1.22	6327.7±3.53
Ni	5.7±0.20	48.6±3.35	67.0±1.15	157.8±2.70
Pb	7.6±0.20	15.8±2.84	40.8±2.70	17.4±1.23
Sr	15.9±0.04	325.6±3.12	322.1±3.20	364.7±4.34
Zn	42.0±0.06	24.7±5.77	354.0±3.61	1324.5±3.50
Cu	2.9±0.05	2.2±0.75	3.8±0.09	2.9±0.09
Co	0.2±0.00	1.4±0.01	2.7±0.09	6.3±0.25
Al	760.3±0.36	4171.2±2.89	3910.9±6.08	3488.0±5.85

Values represent mean ± standard error (n=3).

Fig. 1 Nutrient content in control and metal treated (Pb and Ni) *Brassica juncea* plants

Figure 1 and 2 represent nutrient content in *Brassica juncea* plants treated with T0, T1 and T2, T3 respectively. In Control plants (T0), the higher concentration of elements were found in the order of Mg>Ca>K>Na. However, the minimum concentration in control plant was of cobalt (0.2 ± 0.00 mg/kg). T1 treated plants have maximum and minimum concentrations of Mg (8645 ± 8.09 mg/kg) and Co (1.4 ± 0.01 mg/kg) respectively. T2 treated plants too have maximum and minimum concentrations of Mg (9722 ± 4.01 mg/kg) and Co (2.7 ± 0.15 mg/kg) respectively. While, T3

treated plants have maximum concentrations of K (9724.0 ± 5.56 mg/kg) and minimum of Cu (2.9 ± 0.15 mg/kg) respectively.

SA addition enhanced the uptake of elements such as B, Co, K, Na, Ni, Sr and Zn. Uptake of Pb were highest in plants treated with EDTA (T2), whereas the concentration of Al was maximum in Pb and Ni treated plants (T1). Elements with concentration above 1000 mg/ kg were Ca, Mg, Na, K, Zn and Al.

Fig. 2 Nutrient content in T2 (EDTA+ Pb+Ni) and T3 (SA+ Pb+Ni) treated *Brassica juncea* plants

Calcium was strongly accumulated in the control plants whereas potassium increased as the response to SA treatment. SA treatment increased K and Na levels in plants. Indian mustard showed a more intensive increase in Zn uptake as a response to addition of EDTA and SA compared to control. The highest Zn concentration was found in T3 and the lowest in T1. A study by Maria et al. (2011) found that higher concentrations of Zn and Cd in leaves of *Salix caprea* were associated with increased accumulation of K. Here, the trend of accumulation was in the order of Fe>Mn>Zn>Cu>Cr>Ni>Pb. The overall concentration of heavy metals appeared to be within the limit laid down for safe human consumption (17.35–78.65 µg/g Fe, 16.84–52.94 µg/g Zn, 5.65–7.31 µg/g Cu, 0.51–1.98 µg/g Pb, 4.36–5.69 µg/g Ni and 18.20–33.56 µg/g Mn) (Olowoyo et al. 2012).

Elements Na, K, Mg and Al were found highest in all treatments. Zn, Ca and B contents were higher in SA treated plants.

Fe content was lowest in T1 treatment showing negative impacts of heavy metals on iron. Few elements showed a decrease in concentration due to treatments while others have increased in concentration with metal treatments as compared to control.

Copper was found in the range of 2.2 to 3.8 mg/kg. The permissible limit of Cu in edible plants as per FAO/WHO is 3.0 mg/l (FAO/WHO 2002). Hence, Cu is within permissible limit except in T2 treated plants.

Aluminum ions can cause suppressed root growth and abnormal metabolic effects. So, it is considered toxic to most plants (Ruan and Wong 2004). The concentration of Al in *B. juncea* plants ranged from 760.3±0.63 mg/kg to 4171.2±5.01 mg/kg.

Sasmaz and Sasmaz (2009) reported that strontium contamination can be possible through aerial deposition along with uptake by root and leaf. Sr uptake also depends on soil properties such as pH, organic matter content and ionic composition (Tsialtas et al. 2003). The concentration of Sr was 15.9±0.07 to 364.7±7.51 mg/kg in the present study. The change of transport of some nutrient elements is probably one of the first observed symptoms of effects of Pb, Ni, EDTA and SA. It was found that accumulation of nutrient elements in mustard plants may increase, decrease or be unaffected when plants were treated with lead and nickel (T1). The higher concentrations of lead and nickel may act as toxicants and lessen the uptake of nutrient elements by plants. Sharma and Dubey (2005) suggested physical and chemical mechanisms which decrease uptake of macro and micro nutrients under Pb toxicity. Physical mechanism is based on the competition between metal ions due to similar atomic size. In chemical mechanism, metal-induced disorders in cell metabolism lead to change in membrane enzyme activities and membrane structure. For example, lead and potassium compete for their entry into plant system due to their similar radii (Pb: 1.29 Å and K: 1.33 Å). While, the hypersensitivity of K⁺-ATPase and -SH groups of cell membrane proteins to Pb results in the exit of K⁺ from roots (Pourrut et al. 2011). Pb decreases the level of K, Ca, Fe, Mg, Mn and Zn.

4. Conclusion

The present study provides a broad exploration of the uptake of 15 elements in *Brassica juncea* plants treated with or without Pb+Ni, EDTA and SA. The results indicated that plants had a high concentration of Na, K, Ca and Mg. The uptake of Pb and Ni increased with the chelant EDTA and SA treatments. Lead and nickel affect the uptake, distribution and accumulation of nutrient elements in plants, inducing an increased or decreased concentration of some of them in plants (K, Na, Ca, Fe, Mg, Mn, Cu and Zn). This study can be considered in the alternative utilization of plants harvested in induced phytoextraction technology.

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